

Title

Simultaneous Estimation of Short Chain Fatty Acids by LC-MS/MS Detection Technique.

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Abstract

Pre-analytical derivatization with 3-nitrophenylhydrazine (3NPH) was used to convert for quantitative and qualitative analysis of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) produced by the anaerobic gut microbiota in the large bowel. Understanding the interactions between nutrition, gut microbiota, and host metabolism balance requires both qualitative and quantitative assessments of SCFAs in the intestinal tract and feces. Chemical derivatization is a method for quantifying short-chain fatty acids that employs multiple-reaction monitoring (MRM) and quantum ion electrospray ionization on LC-MS/MS API 3000. The derivatives 3NPH and EDC with pyridine were prepared in a single reaction vessel to achieve accurate quantification and to counteract the matrix effects in ESI. Method validation indicates that the 10 SCFAs have on-column limits of detection and quantification that range from low to high femtomolar. In human feces samples, three out of the ten SCFAs could be identified with intra-day and inter-day precision with a precision of $\leq 3.54\%$ ($n = 6$). The quantitation accuracy ranged from 97.72% to 108.27% ($CVs \leq 8.27\%$, $n = 6$). This method used human feces samples to assess the content and quantities of SCFA. Samples that exhibited a significantly greater molar ratio of branch-chain SCFAs to straight-chain SCFAs than the other were donated by a clinically diagnosed patient. To sum up, this research provides a unique LC-MS/MS method for precise and trustworthy quantification of SCFAs in human feces.

Introduction

Gut bacteria ferment fiber to produce fatty acids (SCFAs), with butyrate, propionate, and acetate being the most common forms. These SCFAs are used by the gut cells for energy and are absorbed into the bloodstream through the stomach wall. SCFAs are crucial for general health, including inflammation, blood sugar regulation, weight maintenance, intestinal health, and mineral absorption. SCFAs support intestinal epithelial cells, which aid in nutrition absorption, food digestion, mucus production, and neuroendocrine cell communication. SCFAs also support tight junctions that hold epithelial cells together, preventing unwanted substances from entering the circulation. Consuming fiber lowers the post-meal blood sugar response, partly due to slower fiber breakdown. SCFAs can also affect blood sugar response by binding to receptors and releasing hormones like GLP-1 and peptide YY, which promote insulin production and reduce glucagon levels. Eating fiber helps reduce blood sugar response after a meal by slowing down the breakdown of sugar. Some saturated fatty acids (SFAs) may also play a role in blood sugar control by triggering the release of hormones like GLP-1 and peptide YY from gut cells. These hormones lower blood glucose by stimulating insulin release and slowing the release of glucagon. SCFAs also influence glycolysis, gluconeogenesis, and glycogen synthesis. However, the exact impact of SCFAs on blood sugar responses after a meal is still being studied. They may also help maintain a healthy weight by increasing the sensation of feeling full and promoting the release of leptin, a hormone that reduces appetite. Evidence in humans suggests that SCFAs help control blood sugar levels and maintain a healthy weight.

Materials and Methods

Acetic Acid (HPLC/LC-MS grade), Propionic Acid (HPLC/LC-MS grade), Butyric Acid (HPLC/LC-MS grade), Formic Acid (HPLC/LC-MS grade), Acetonitrile (LC-MS grade), Methanol (LC-MS grade), Water (Milli-Q/HPLC Grade), 3-Nitrophenyl Hydrazine (3NPH) (GR/AR), 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) (GR/AR), Pyridine (GR/AR).

The Process Involves the Derivatization of a Standard Mix Solution of SCFA.

Derivatization was performed by adding 200 μL of a SCFA standard mix solution containing 6 SCFA standards (acetate, propionate and butyrate at a final concentration of 0.250 μM to 250 μM each) in $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{ACN}$ (50:50, v/v) and 10 μL of 200mM 3-Nitrophenyl Hydrazine (NPH) and Add 10 μL of 120mM 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) and vortex to mix. 100 μL of Methanol and vortex to mix. Incubate at 40°C for 40 minutes and Cool in an Ice bath for 5 minutes Add

280µL of 10% Acetonitrile and vortex to mix. And Take 30µL Above. Add 970µL of 10% Acetonitrile and vortex to mix. wet ice bath with regular mixing, and submitted to LC-MS/MS for further analysis.

Preparation of Calibration Curve Standards

A standard mix solution containing all SCFA's eight standards (STD1 to STD8 for acetate, propionate, and butyrate at a final concentration of 0.250µM to 250µM each) was prepared in H₂O/ACN (50:50, v/v).

Preparation of Quality Control Samples

A Quality Control Sample containing all SCFA's four quality control samples (HQC, MQC, LQC, and LLOQ QC for acetate, propionate, and butyrate at a final concentration of 210.000, 125.000, 0.750, and 0.250µM each) was prepared in H₂O/ACN (50:50, v/v).

General Procedure for Faeces Sample Collection

Feces samples will be collected in a flatbottom polypropylene container or specimen container and stored immediately at 2-8°C, the collected sample will be transferred to the laboratory within 24 hours until further processing samples will be stored at -80°C/-20°C. The required sample amount should be more than 5.0g wet weight will be collected.

Process of Faecal Homogenate Mixture Preparation

Weigh 2.0 g of feces and add 2.0 mL of Acetonitrile, immediately Homogenize (Vortexes) by using a homogenizer for 5 minutes, this Homogenate mixture will be centrifuged at 4500 rpm at 10 °C for 10 minutes, after centrifugation separated 1.0 mL of supernatant and add 1.0 mL of HPLC grade water, vortex it and store in deep freezer (-70°C).

(Between Homogenate mixture preparation steps will be carried out on ice)

Preparation of Test Sample Mixtures

Retrieve samples from the deep freezer and allow them to thaw in ice cold water bath and Vortex to mix. Centrifuge all the samples for 5 minutes at 4000rpm at about 5.0°C. (Centrifugation is not required for freshly spiked samples) Derivatization was performed by adding 200 µL of above prepared Faecal Homogenate Mixture supernatant of the test sample mixture and 10µL of 200mM 3-Nitrophenyl

Hydrazine (NPH) and Adding 10 μ L of 120mM 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) and vortex to mix. 100 μ L of Methanol and vortex to mix. Incubate at 40°C for 40 minutes and Cool in an Ice bath for 5 minutes, Add 280 μ L of 10% Acetonitrile and vortex to mix. And Take 30 μ L Above. Add 970 μ L of 10% Acetonitrile and vortex to mix. wet ice bath with regular mixing, and submitted to LC-MS/MS for further analysis.

LC-MS/MS Sample Analysis

LC-MS/MS analysis was performed on a ShimadzuTM Prominence high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) system coupled to an AB SCIEXTM triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (API 3000) equipped with an electrospray ionization probe. The HPLC-MS/MS platform was controlled by a Synchronised software AnalystTM Version 1.6.2 data system. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Kinetics C18, 100 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m C18 column using a binary solvent system composed of LC-MS grade 0.1% Formic Acid in Acetonitrile (Solvent A) and LC-MS grade 0.1% Formic Acid in Water (solvent B). In the ratio of 30:70 respectively for pump A and pump B. The following 8 min run time. The flow rate was 600 μ L min⁻¹ and the sample injection volume was 10 μ L. The auto sampler was kept at 5°C and the column at 40°C.

MS/MS data were acquired in positive electrospray ionization mode with the mass spectrometer operating in selected reaction monitoring (SRM) mode. Fragmentation parameters were optimized using the Tune program with direct infusion of the derivatized analytical grade standards (100 μ M each in H₂O/MeOH (50:50, v/v)). The derivatized SCFA's have similar breakdown curves, with the most abundant fragment ion detected (m/z 94.1; protonated aniline (C₆H₈N)) resulting from the cleavage of the amide bond, at a collision energy (CE) of 14-17eV. The second most abundant fragment ion detected, with a relative intensity of 60–80%, was m/z 77.0 (28-33eV CE) characteristic of the benzene group (C₆H₅). Similar results were obtained for the derivatized deuterated standards except that the aniline fragment ion was m/z 95.1 at CE 18eV. Subsequently, the following transitions, corresponding to the derivatized SCFAs were monitored, with a scan time of 0.02 sec and a fixed collision energy of 14eV: [M+H]⁺ m/z 196.100 \rightarrow 137.100 for Acetate, 210.100 \rightarrow 137.100 for Propionate and 224.100 \rightarrow 137.100 for butyrate (21eV for the collision energy). Electrospray ionization source conditions were as follows: spray voltage of 3000 V, source temperature of 400°C, and delustering potential of 90, 120, and 120 respectively.

The determination of the lower limit of detection (LLOD) and lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) was based on the analysis of the peak's height for the analyte signal (S) and the baseline noise (N) of

chromatographic peaks corresponding to samples prepared as detailed in “preparation of calibration curves” section. The final concentration of each solution tested was as follows: 250.000, 200.000, 150.000, 100.000, 50.000, 25.000, 0.500, 0.250 μ M for Acetate, Propionate and Butyrate. Each sample was injected in a singlet. LLOD and LLOQ were defined as the concentrations where the signal-to-noise (S/N) was greater than or equal to 3 and greater than or equal to 10 respectively.

For the evaluation of the precision and accuracy of the analytical method, three different Precision and accuracy batch samples were prepared as per the sample preparation method with the respective Calibration Curve Standards and quality control samples at LLOQ QC to HQC level concentration. The final concentrations of 210.000, 125.000, 0.750, and 0.250 μ M each analyte respectively. The derivatization step was carried out as described above. Before LC-MS/MS analysis, samples were diluted 1:100, with Acetonitrile v/v). The precision of the analytical method was estimated by calculating the relative standard deviation (RSD, expressed in percentage), whereas the determination of accuracy was evaluated by calculating the percent error (%Error or % Bias), both based on the analysis of three replicates of experiment injections for intra-day and inter-day variation determination). For inter-day variation determination, data were collected over two consecutive days.

Results and Discussion

Method for quantifying SCFAs by LC-MS/MS

A defined mixture of acetate, propionate, and butyrate standards (1.0 M each, final concentration) was subjected to derivatization with aniline, as depicted in the reaction scheme, and submitted to LC-MS/MS analysis. As expected, derivatized SCFA analytes co-eluted ([Fig 1](#)), were easily distinguishable by m/z and had peak intensities proportional to the relative concentrations of each other's ratios.

Fig 1. Derivatized SCFA Analytes Co-Eluted

To determine the linear range of detection for aniline-derivatized SCFAs using our LC-MS/MS method, calibration curves were generated using an equimolar standard mix solution. Linear relationships were apparent for acetate, propionate, and butyrate derivatized standards ($r^2 > 0.997$ for all eight standards). The slopes of the regression lines for all SCFA's were linear and calculated as ($y=7.71e+004x + 536$ for Acetate), ($y=7.17e+004x + -338$ for Propionate) and ($y=9.16e+004x + -368$ for Butyrate) (Fig 2a to 2c).

Fig 2a. Calibration Curve of Acetate

Fig 2b. Calibration Curve of Propionate

Fig 2b. Calibration Curve of Butyrate

The lower limit of detection (LLOD) and the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) for all three selected SCFAs were determined with standards derivatized in H₂O/ACN (50:50, v/v). The LLOD was 0.250 μ M for Acetate, Propionate, and Butyrate. The LLOQ for 0.250 μ M for Acetate, Propionate, and Butyrate. As the quantification of SCFAs in the developed method is based on the accurate determination of the 1:1:1 ratio of analytes, the intra- and inter-day precision and accuracy were evaluated using samples, derivatized in H₂O/ACN (50:50, v/v), with two different known ratios. The intra-day method precision, expressed as percent relative standard deviation, was between 6–7%, whereas the inter-day precision (assessed over 2 days) was less than 3%. The accuracy of the method, expressed as percent error or percent bias, ranged from 0.6 to 15 and 1.0 to 15% for intra- and inter-day accuracy, respectively.

Table 1

LLOD and LLOQ for the selected SCFAs.

Analyte	LLOD (μ M)	LLOQ (μ M)
Acetic acid	0.250	0.250
Propionic acid	0.250	0.250
Butyric acid	0.250	0.250

Abbreviations: LLOD, the lower limit of detection. LLOQ, the lower limit of quantification.

Intra-and inter-day precision (%RSD) and accuracy (%CV) of the LC-MS/MS method.

Table 2

Precision and Accuracy (P&A) Back Calculated Concentrations for Calibration Curve Standards of Acetate, Propionate, and Butyrate

	STD8	STD7	STD6	STD5	STD4	STD3	STD2	STD1
For Acetate	μ M	μ M	μ M					
	0.250	0.500	25.000	50.000	100.000	150.000	200.000	250.000
Calculated Concentration	0.255	0.480	25.054	48.243	99.592	148.374	208.093	256.741
Mean	0.2550	0.4800	25.0540	48.2430	99.5920	148.3740	208.0930	256.7410
% Mean Accuracy	102.00	96.00	100.22	96.49	99.59	98.92	104.05	102.70

% RSD	2.00	-4.00	0.22	-3.51	-0.41	-1.08	4.05	2.70
n	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
For Propionate	STD8	STD7	STD6	STD5	STD4	STD3	STD2	STD1
	µM	µM	µM	µM	µM	µM	µM	µM
	0.250	0.500	25.000	50.000	100.000	150.000	200.000	250.000
Calculated Concentration	0.254	0.485	23.101	46.271	96.406	156.373	212.616	273.701
Mean	0.2540	0.4850	23.1010	46.2710	96.4060	156.3730	212.6160	273.7010
% Mean Accuracy	101.60	97.00	92.40	92.54	96.41	104.25	106.31	109.48
% RSD	1.60	-3.00	-7.60	-7.46	-3.59	4.25	6.31	9.48
n	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
For Butyrate	STD8	STD7	STD6	STD5	STD4	STD3	STD2	STD1
	µM	µM	µM	µM	µM	µM	µM	µM
	0.250	0.500	25.000	50.000	100.000	150.000	200.000	250.000
Calculated Concentration	0.262	0.451	23.832	45.804	100.925	153.103	216.914	266.107
Mean	0.2620	0.4510	23.8320	45.8040	100.9250	153.1030	216.9140	266.1070
% Mean Accuracy	104.80	90.20	95.33	91.61	100.93	102.07	108.46	106.44
% RSD	4.80	-9.80	-4.67	-8.39	0.92	2.07	8.46	6.44
n	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Table 3

Back Calculated Concentrations for Quality Control Samples for Acetate, Propionate, and Butyrate (Within / Intra Run)

For Acetate	LLOQ QC	LQC	MQC	HQC
	µM	µM	µM	µM
	0.250	0.750	125.000	210.000
	0.252	0.813	124.202	213.106
	0.250	0.752	123.487	211.479
	0.242	0.762	121.527	215.237
	0.249	0.783	123.437	222.854

	0.231	0.767	120.854	221.577
	0.255	0.760	119.357	219.125
Mean	0.2465	0.7728	122.1440	217.2297
SD	0.00873	0.02221	1.87206	4.65124
% CV	3.54	2.87	1.53	2.14
% RSD	-1.40	3.04	-2.28	3.44
% Mean Accuracy	98.60	103.04	97.72	103.44
n	6	6	6	6

	LLOQ QC	LQC	MQC	HQC
	µM	µM	µM	µM
For Propionate	0.250	0.750	125.000	210.000
	0.250	0.748	129.283	222.317
	0.252	0.768	132.339	225.612
	0.247	0.692	126.920	226.993
	0.254	0.767	126.753	216.512
	0.238	0.766	127.015	237.746
	0.234	0.758	128.838	235.083
	Mean	0.2458	0.7498	128.5247
SD	0.00806	0.02933	2.15477	7.92229
% CV	3.28	3.91	1.68	3.48
% RSD	-1.68	-0.03	2.82	8.27
% Mean Accuracy	98.32	99.97	102.82	108.27
n	6	6	6	6

	LLOQ QC	LQC	MQC	HQC
	µM	µM	µM	µM
For Butyrate	0.250	0.750	125.000	210.000
	0.267	0.702	128.660	218.667
	0.259	0.744	128.163	221.879
	0.239	0.728	125.737	227.008
	0.251	0.754	122.869	220.657
	0.239	0.776	126.731	235.623
	0.232	0.773	126.739	230.849
	Mean	0.2478	0.7462	126.4832
SD	0.01348	0.02813	2.06428	6.57488
% CV	5.44	3.77	1.63	2.91
% RSD	-0.88	-0.51	1.19	7.51
% Mean Accuracy	99.12	99.49	101.19	107.51
n	6	6	6	6

Abbreviations: SD, standard deviation. % RSD, percent relative standard deviation. %CV, percent coefficient variation.

Conclusion

Under the precise ICH M 10 Harmonised Guidelines for Analytical Technique Validation, the analytical technique was validated. The information in this method validation report supports the specificity, accuracy, reproducibility, and robustness of the analytical technique utilized to estimate acetate, propionate, and butyrate using LC-MS/MS detection. The results additionally indicate that the technique applies to the estimation of acetate, propionate, and butyrate at 0.250 $\mu\text{M}/\text{mL}$ to 250.000 $\mu\text{M}/\text{mL}$ calibration concentrations range.

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